

MEDICAL SCIENCES

ASSESSMENT OF PUBLIC SATISFACTION WITH THE QUALITY OF PROVIDED MEDICAL SERVICES

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Abstract

The health care system of the Republic of Belarus occupies a worthy place among the health care systems of developed countries of the European region. However, it is still undergoing dynamic reforms. An important indicator of the quality of medical care is patient satisfaction, which depends on the initial expectations of patients regarding the ability of health care institutions to meet their needs and increases proportionally to the rise of the level of technical equipment and professional training of the staff, which makes the satisfaction of these expectations quite a difficult task.

Keywords: quality of medical care; health care efficiency; satisfaction with medical care, public health care institution, private medical centre.

Introduction. According to the Constitution of the Republic of Belarus, every citizen has a guaranteed right to health care, including free treatment in state health care institutions. In order to improve the quality of medical care, the Government of the Republic of Belarus, the Ministry of Health and the management of health care institutions constantly monitor the quality of medical care.

The commercialization of health care inevitably exacerbates the contradiction between economic rationalism and medical humanism, the solution to which lies in ensuring medical care that has the maximum effect at a reasonable cost [1].

The greatest difficulty in assessing the quality of medical care is caused by such a criterion as patient satisfaction. The reasons are obvious: this indicator is subjective and influenced by many constantly changing factors [2].

The relevance of this study is due to the need to improve the efficiency of the health care system in terms of quality and accessibility of medical care. The observed trend of citizens' increasing appeal to private medical organizations requires an analysis of the results of the work of private and public health care institutions, and a study of patients' satisfaction with the medical services provided to them.

The purpose of the research is identifying key differences in patients' attitudes towards accessibility and

quality of medical care in state and private health care organizations in the Republic of Belarus.

Research materials and methods:

In the Republic of Belarus, as in many countries of the world, the evaluation of the quality of medical care by patients should be realized through the assessment of satisfaction with

- competence of the personnel;
- accessibility of information about diagnosis, methods of treatment, dynamics of health status and results of medical treatment;
- provision with medicines;
- conditions of medical care and technical support;
- attitude and competence of employees of the medical organization providing medical care.

To study these an anonymous survey was conducted using a questionnaire developed by the Department of Public Health and Health Care of the Grodno State Medical University. Statistical processing of the obtained data was carried out using STATISTICA-10.0 (Stat Soft Inc.) software.

Results and discussion: A total of 355 patients who had applied to the state and private health care institutions of the Republic of Belarus participated in the questionnaire survey. Of these, 49.1% were female and 40.9% were male. The distribution of the participants in terms of age is presented in Table 1.

Table 1

The distribution of the respondents in terms of age

Age	18 – 29	30 – 39	40 – 49	50 – 59	60+
Quantity, %	15,2%	20%	24,9%	13,9%	26%

The share of patients who applied for an appointment in a given health care institution for the first time in the current year was 48.4%, for the second time – 29.8%, and more than twice – 21.8%. At the same time, almost all the respondents (87.3%) applied to private medical centres for one reason or another.

92% of the respondents from among the patients of private medical centres were fully satisfied with the duration and conditions of waiting for a doctor's appointment (availability of necessary information, sufficient seats during the waiting time, availability of visual information, etc.), but 8% of the respondents could not answer this question. In public health care institutions, 46.4% of the survey participants were fully satisfied with the duration and conditions of waiting for a doctor's appointment. 23.6% of the respondents noted long queues, unclear location of offices, incorrect appointment schedule, insufficient time for one patient and, accordingly, for a conversation between the patient and the doctor. And 30% of the survey participants found it difficult to answer this question.

The attitude of medical staff to patients (friendliness, politeness, willingness to help, interest in results) in private medical centers was rated highly by 96.4% of respondents, only 1.9% gave a low rating. At the same time, 1.7% of the respondents were not able to evaluate a private medical institution according to this parameter. In state medical institutions, about half of patients (47.4%) rated the attitude of medical staff highly, 14.2% gave a low rating for this criterion. In the comments to the answers they pointed out the low interest of the doctors in the treatment of the patient, formal attitude, tactlessness, familiarity and even rudeness of the medical staff. At the same time, 38.4% of the respondents were not able to evaluate the medical institutions according to this criterion, perhaps due to the fact that they received the necessary medical care in full despite some inconveniences.

The comfort of staying in state healthcare facilities (convenience, comfort) was highly rated by 57% of patients. Almost a fifth of the respondents (19%) gave an unsatisfactory rating. In private centers, 75.9% of patients rated the comfort of their stay highly, and 2% were dissatisfied.

Assessment of accessibility and adequacy of diagnostic examinations (from the patient's point of view) in health care institutions of both forms of ownership did not differ significantly. In state health care institutions 50.7% of the respondents rated it as high. In private health centers this parameter was evaluated as high by 57.7% of the respondents.

Patients' satisfaction with the results of medical treatment also differs only slightly. In public health care institutions, slightly more than half of the respondents (53%) and in private centers, 55.9% of the respondents were satisfied with the results of medical treatment.

52.1% of the respondents were satisfied with the technical condition of the department, repair of the premises and space of the premises in public health care institutions. And in private centers their number was 58.7%.

Patients' satisfaction with sanitary and hygienic conditions in public health care facilities was 52.4%. Private medical centers were rated highly on this parameter by 64% of respondents. More than a half (53%)

of the respondents were satisfied with the provision of medicines and consumables in public health care institutions, in private centers – 73% of the survey participants.

The actions of medical staff in the performance of their duties in public health care institutions were highly appreciated by 56% of respondents. The number of satisfied patients in private medical centers slightly exceeded this indicator and amounted to 60.8%.

The level of trust in medical personnel in public health care institutions was 32.4%, while this indicator reached 74% in private centers.

In both public and private health care organizations, patients had to pay for additional treatment or diagnostic procedures in 57% and 58%, respectively.

Conclusion. Increasing public satisfaction with the possibility of receiving quality medical care is an important task of reforming the healthcare system. In the search for new approaches to improving the availability, quality and culture of medical care against the background of limited economic opportunities of health care and improvement of financial relations, the opinion of patients is one of the criteria for assessing the activities of medical institutions.

As a result of the study it is possible to conclude that satisfaction with the work of the state health care system remains at an average level.

Technical equipment of both private and public health care institutions is quite highly appreciated by the survey participants, however satisfaction resulting from the fulfillment of expectations, depends not only on the technical capabilities of modern medicine and organizational mechanisms of care delivery, but also on a multitude of cultural, psychological and social factors.

In the work of public health care institutions, first of all it is necessary to pay close attention to the problems of interaction between patients and medical personnel, since many problems of negative perception of health care institutions can be solved without significant financial investments. It is necessary to change the attitude towards the patient, to reduce the waiting time for an appointment and to solve the problem of shortage of specialists in certain medical institutions.

Private medical centers were rated higher in terms of quality of medical care. However, the high cost of services provided is a significant cause of patients' dissatisfaction.

Dissatisfaction in a number of cases with the availability and quality of medical care both in public and private health care institutions, on the one hand, dictates the need to improve the work of medical organizations, on the other hand, requires revision of doctor-patient relations, improvement of deontological literacy and professionalism of medical personnel.

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